

EXPRESSION OF FEELINGS OF LOVE FOR THE MOTHERLAND IN THE POETRY
OF MAQSUD SHAYKHZODA

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Abstract. This article tells about the fact that educating a harmonious generation in the spirit of patriotism, teaching is one of the most basic tasks before our state, in particular, the poetry of the poet, playwright, translator, scientist, educator Maqsud Shaykhzoda is based on the highest feelings.

Keywords: Heroism, tolerance and harmony, Homeland, patriotism.

ВЫРАЖЕНИЕ ЧУВСТВА ЛЮБВИ К РОДИНЕ В ПОЭЗИИ МАКСУДА
ШАЙХЗОДЫ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассказывается о том, что воспитание гармоничного поколения в духе патриотизма, преподавания является одной из важнейших задач перед нашим государством, в частности, поэзия поэта, драматурга, переводчика, ученого, просветителя Максуда Шайхзода основана на высшие чувства.

Ключевые слова: Героизм, толерантность и согласие, Родина, патриотизм.

The focus of all reforms carried out in Uzbekistan is young people. It is for this reason that educating a harmonious generation in the spirit of patriotism, teaching is one of the most basic tasks before our state. Teaching young people to independently think and view the world, modern knowledge and thinking is the main thing, to love their motherland, to speak their native language and foreign languages correctly and fluently is considered the main task for every educator.

Today, literature relies on the theory of personality-oriented education in developing the methodological foundations of teaching. "...in this place, we are talking, first of all, about the creation of the necessary environment and conditions for the wide promotion of the rich history of our country, its unique culture, the transmission of the achievements of World Science and literature among young people and the population.

The restoration of lost traditions, the awareness of the uniqueness of the culture of each ethnic group are the priorities of our era. The state seeks to educate tolerance and mutual respect in the younger generation. The priority of any state is patriotic education. In addition to personal

aspirations, a person needs universal values, and one of them is a sense of patriotism, this patriotism, love for his homeland, this is a moral trait that connects all people to a single society. Only a society united by love for its homeland can make the state holistic and prosperous. Patriotic education goes through several stages: love for the motherland from love for your family. Love for the motherland is the highest level of patriotism. In recent years, special attention has been paid to teaching students to analyze a work of art.

This issue has been attracting the attention of scientists for many years. In this regard, the work of the poet, playwright, translator, scientist, educator Maqsd Shaykhzoda is based on pure love, relationships between people, friendly ties, impeccable thoughts and the highest feelings of patriotism. The poetry of Maqsd Shaykhzoda is closely related to modernity in each line of his civic lyrics is very relevant. Maqsd Shaykhzoda's poems are deep in content, very logical in meaning. The basis of his poetry is heroic, psychological, dramatic processes.

His 437-page book, "25 years of controversy", also features examples of native lyricism. In the present, we are creating conditions for the revival of the Customs and achievements of our past ancestors. It serves as a factor in ensuring tolerance, peace and stability to young people. An integral part of the formation of patriotism among modern youth is education on the example of the heroes of the Great Patriotic War.

During the years of World War II, Maqsd Shaykhzoda published several collections of poetry: "What is the Battle for?" , " Fight and song" , " The Heart Speaks" , " born with Thunder". In parallel, the Comrade wrote the poems "eleventh", "Zhenya", "third son", "Elder" about Okhunboboyev. Knowledge of historical events provides the basis for the formation of patriotic feelings among modern youth.

The theme of the Great Patriotic War and patriotism did not lose its relevance in the work of Maqsd Shaykhzoda, since this event influenced every family. Victory Day is widely celebrated every year in countries that have fought against fascist invaders. Thousands of young people died on the battlefield. They were inspired by the idea of winning. They gave their lives for our youth and our state so that we could prosper.

Everyone should be grateful that they breathe deeply in a free country. It should be noted that patriotism is manifested in the unity of spirituality, citizenship and social activity of a person, which is formed under the influence of many factors. In this case, education occupies the main role. After all, it always has a decisive influence on the formation of an individual and, as a result, on the well-being of the whole society.

Young people themselves must participate in solving the problems of patriotic education of the modern generation, realize the importance of their activities in the life of the motherland and love, know and respect its culture, traditions and history. The sense of patriotism is inherently multifaceted. This is not only love for the motherland, but also love for their native places and pride for their people and the desire to feel indistinguishable from the world around them, to preserve and increase the wealth of their country.

During the Uig Patriotic War, Maqsud Shaykhzoda combined the best poetic traditions of Uzbek folklore and classical poetry with the achievements of modern literature. Maqsud Shaykhzoda writes works in the genres of classical Eastern poetry. The theme of patriotism is raised in the "poem about Tashkent" ("Tashkent", "quarter century sofa" collection of Selected Works, the lyrical Collection "years and paths", "perspective", "lyrical and philosophical works".

The theme of Maqsud Shaikhzoda's patriotic upbringing in the tragedy "Jaloliddin Manguberdi" historically accurately and truthfully described the martial courage of the last Khwarazmian King, who fought against the Mongol conquerors for the freedom and independence of his land. In 1988, "Jaloliddin Manguberdi" was first published in full print in the Uzbek-language writer's book "The Immortal World".

This work, in the spirit of heroism, which exudes a sense of patriotism in the hearts of people, has not lost its relevance today. Even after many years, the works of the Shaikhzoda have shown their strength. In the process of reading the work, we find out that Maqsud Shaikhzoda has adequately approached the history of our people, including the fate and struggle of Jalaliddin Manguberdi, defended the truth. The work "Jaloliddin Manguberdi" evokes a spirit of self-awareness, pride in nationality in young people. That is why these works once again proved the sharpness of Shaykhzoda's writing mind and creativity. Another great contribution of Maqsud Shaikhzoda to Uzbek literature is the tragedy "Mirzo Ulugbek".

The tragedy was written in 1964, the same year the work was put on the stage of the Hamza theater, later a feature film was created on its basis. Reading the above-mentioned dramatic works of Maqsud Shaykhzoda and a number of other examples of creativity, we witness in each of them the skillful expression of feelings of high patriotism. The historical memory of the people is passed down from generation to generation. Spiritual and cultural values created in the past become the property of modern society. A vivid example of this is the works of Maqsud Shaikhzoda, written in the spirit of such patriotism and love for the motherland.

In conclusion, as the president of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted in his speeches: "at the moment there is no way between young people without forming a stable civil position,

without developing initiative, independence and being ready to defend the interests of their country.” One of the important tasks of the process of raising young people at the present stage of the development of education is the formation and development of a sense of patriotism in students through our invaluable masterpieces, since without this feeling it is impossible to talk about the upbringing of a truly harmonious person.

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